

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

2nd TNA Call Documentation - User

STORIES TNA2 POST RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Artificial Intelligence for Microgrid Energy Storage Systems
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	AIMESS
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	PROTEAS – The Cyprus Institute
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	Smart Grid – Microgrid Operation and Controls – Smart Management Power of Hybrid Storage Systems – Artificial Intelligence - Spiking Neural Network
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	5 July 2023
Departure date (from town where RI located)	22 July 2023
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	5 July 2023
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	22 July 2023
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	2
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	Sundays (9-July and 16-July 2023)
Number of days using the RI	16
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>The aim of the proposed work is the design and realization of an Artificial Intelligence (AI) interface, which will interact with the various energy sources and control the Energy Transmission Unit in order to optimally distribute the produced from the Microgrid energy to a hybrid storage system. More specifically, the Microgrid structure comprises four different renewable energy sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A Photovoltaic Array (Electricity) • Wind Power Generation from wind turbines (Electricity) 	

- Concentrating Solar Power from a Stirling Dish (Electricity)
- Concentrating Solar Power from a Tower in a Heliostat Field (Heat Production)

The AI interface is connected with these energy sources through the Energy Production Monitoring System, which is a field bus connection over Ethernet realized with well established, industrial communication protocols. This interface will act either directly with the various subsystem controllers or with the main Control System of the facility, by monitoring and selecting all the appropriate parameters for establishing the functionality status of each device.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

As already proposed, the implementation scheme of the current project is divided in three phases. In the first stage, where the appropriate software model is already constructed, the program will run in a simulation mode. Data streams from the energy production Microgrid components through the monitoring system will be collected and compared in real-time with the model output values by adjusting all free parameters. During the second phase, the real data input stream will be utilized by the Spiking Neural Network (SNN) to train the relevant network architecture and to produce correct decisions for the energy transmission to the hybrid storage system. The third phase is a final check of the proposed AI model and its reliability by directly comparing and analyzing the obtained storage decisions for the Microgrid energy production in real time and in different time periods with various environmental conditions.

During the first half of the PROTEAS Facility access following tasks have been performed:

- (1) A core software system in the form of a Spiking Neural Network (SNN) has been designed with the relevant architecture to meet all parameter requirements. The selection of this network type is necessarily dictated by the nature of the time characteristics and the different temporal character these input signals may have. The input parameters of the model were appropriately adjusted to the facility's energy source parameters and sample data were collected and analysed.
- (2) The dataflow to the AI interface is in addition supplemented also with environmental parameters, like wind speed, wind direction, solar DNI values and various temperatures, which are periodically submitted from a Baseline Surface Radiation Network (BSRN) tower and they support the utilization of the collected data samples. For this purpose, a special DAQ interface to the previous SNN model was constructed.
- (3) Several data sets have been collected during the access in the PROTEAS facility. They are used to train the AI network and to produce some preliminary decisions for the energy transmission to the hybrid storage system. The output values are translated in actuator signals which are directly compared with the overall Microgrid energy production in real time and in different time periods with various environmental conditions.

This work will be continued and completed in the second phase of the PROTEAS Facility access, planned for the first months of the coming year.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

Some preliminary scientific results are already obtained from the analysis of the energy production monitoring system in relation to the environmental data streams collected with the Baseline Surface Radiation Network (BSRN) station.

The main task of the AI System is twofold: It has to efficiently learn and to correctly decode all possible correlations between the environmental parameters and the energy production monitored values, so that it can predict in an incremental way the expected energy production from the different subsystems. In addition and after a successful completion of the learning phase, the underlying Neural Network must be able to act as a storage management system,

which efficiently supervises the associated actuators of the Energy Transmission Control in order to decide and direct the produced energy flow to the appropriate medium in the existing hybrid storage system: Chemical Storage (batteries array) for the produced electricity and Thermal Storage (Molten Salt) for the case of heat. Although with the existing data the training phase is not yet finalized, it seems that both tasks can be successfully fulfilled.

As earlier mentioned, the third phase of this project is a final check of the proposed AI model and its reliability by directly comparing and analyzing the obtained storage decisions for the Microgrid energy production in real time and in different time periods with various environmental conditions. The final product will be in the form of a software package, easily adaptable to any other Microgrid structure. Input and output signals will be generalized in a universal format to cover the needs of other similar facilities. It is also foreseen the hardware implementation of the developed Spiking Neural Network-based model on the ARTIX-7 FPGA (Field Programmable Gate Array) platform. The proposed work does not include any special requirements regarding the hosting facility, while the test and implementation objectives are clear and characterized by a very low risk assessment.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

In the last years, a variety of AI algorithms have shown great promise in a large number of applications for power system control operation and control and their potential application in Microgrid structures. Deep Learning (DL) and Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) have recently demonstrated their excellence in tackling problems pertinent to decision making. One of the most important technical and economical tools in this regard is the Optimal Power Flow (OPF). As a fundamental optimization tool in the operation and planning fields, OPF has an undeniable role in the power system.

The proposed work belongs to the same thematic category dealing with Microgrid AI and differentiates from the above mentioned techniques in the following two points:

(i) The Artificial Intelligence System tries to associate energy production data with meteorological and other environmental parameters, in order to better estimate and accurately predict energy generation flows for a given Microgrid structure. Consequently, it will be an ideal software package to simulate energy generation flows from different subsystems. Furthermore, the model intelligence focuses on the optimal decision making for the energy transmission control flow to a hybrid storage medium.

(ii) Due to various time characteristics of the input signals, the underlying network architecture is realized with a Spike Neural Network. The introduction of this network type accounts for the different temporal character of the incoming signals and provides a more effective solution to overcome usual problems related to conventional network architectures with continuous activation functions.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

Main achievements during the first half access of the PROTEAS facility are summarized as follows:

- ☑ A core software system in the form of a Spiking Neural Network (SNN) has been designed and realized *in situ*, running on a simple computer platform.
- ☑ Model input parameters were connected and adjusted with the monitoring system of the main Control System of PROTEAS.

Extra dataflow to the model was realized with the construction of a special interface to the Baseline Surface Radiation Network (BSRN) tower.

Training of the Spiking Neural Network was successfully performed with many data samples collected during the stay and for various environmental conditions.

The second half of the project includes the final implementation of the trained software in an ARTIX-7 FPGA (Field Programmable Gate Array) platform and the functionality check of the output signals to the Microgrid actuators.

Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)

There was an easy access in the main Control System of the PROTEAS facility and all the associated equipment. The personnel were very supportive in explaining the functionality of the system and helping to realize the required electrical and electronic connections for the collection of the input signals.

There were no technical problems or other issues at all!

Intended publications

A joint journal article publication is foreseen, to encompass the project results and enhance further the collaboration among the researchers.

Data management

Obtained data are locally stored and can be further used for future training and other analyses.

Conclusions / additional comments

The first part of the project has been successfully conducted and the obtained results guarantee a successful outcome of the proposed work.

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS> ? (necessary)

Yes No

Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction

Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments

Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

[Comment]

Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed

1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)

	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Comment]</i>	
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please specify any problems]</i>	
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please specify]</i>	
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please specify]</i>	
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<i>[Please provide details]</i>	

Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The programme was very supportive and helped to access a state of the art facility to realize innovative ideas.					
Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research					
<i>[Please provide suggestions for specific type of facilities missing (RI gaps) or measurement / experiments you would like to perform which cannot be done on current StoRIES facilities]</i>					
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.					
<i>[Your suggestions]</i>					
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support					

Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please specify how you learned about the pro-active innovation support]</i>					
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>[Please provide details]</i>					

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.